

TECHNOLOGY OF PROCESSING SHAPED SURFACES

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Abstract: *The article discusses the technology of processing shaped surfaces, cutters used for shaped surfaces and ways of using them.*

Key Words: *Technology, shaped cutter, shaped surfaces, shape, methods.*

The main part

The formation of shaped surfaces during turning occurs by rotating curved formers around the axis of the products. The formers can also be combinations of lines of different profiles that create a certain configuration of the part during rotation. There are several ways to manufacture and control the shape of products with shaped surfaces, including using:

- template;
- shaped tools;
- copy;
- a combination of these methods.

When using templates, the cutter is fed both longitudinally and transversely. After cutting a certain layer thickness, a template is applied to the part to determine the size of the next layer to be cut.

The simplest way to obtain a shaped surface of a part is to use a cutter with a cutting edge that repeats a given curvilinear generatrix.

The use of a copier makes it possible to obtain the most accurate configuration of the part. Sometimes in practice it is necessary to use a combination of all these methods – most often it concerns the grinding of elongated products using carbide and high-speed tools.

Modern machine tools ensure high accuracy of workpiece processing, while the part must be securely fixed in the spindle or machine centers. In cases where the length of the workpiece significantly exceeds its diameter, additional supports – lunettes are used. Thus, it is possible to significantly increase the rigidity of the installation of the part, which contributes to the accuracy of processing.

The practical use of incisors with a curved configuration is limited by the width of their cutting part, which should not exceed 60 mm. The radius of cast iron and steel billets made of cast iron or steel is limited to 20 millimeters. In such cases, it is important to take into account that the operating forces in the cutting zone must correspond to the overall rigidity of all components of the LED system.

If it is necessary to obtain a radius of the workpiece exceeding 20 mm, through cutters are used, the radius of rounding of which is less than the radius of rounding of the mating part, for example, a bearing.

Shaped cutters:

a – one-piece; б - with mechanical fastening of the cutting part; в - disk

Processing with through-pass cutters

In a single production, the requirements for manufacturing accuracy are small, so the grinding of shaped surfaces on machines is carried out manually, and the quality of execution is ensured due to the high qualification of workers. This is due to the lack of automatic settings: the cutting process and the accuracy of the work are provided by the performer, combining the longitudinal and transverse movement of the cutter. To obtain practical processing skills, the finished part of a given shaped profile is installed in the spindle of the machine, along which the turner manually, using the handles of the machine support, moves the cutter so that its cutting part follows the contour of the product.

The turning process takes place in two positions. First, the handle blank is fixed in the machine spindle for the cylindrical part A, processing is performed with a stepped shaped surface (B, C, D, E) of the shank. Before that, a marking along the length is applied to the workpiece. Then the part is turned over, fixed to the

processed step shank and the processing of part G of the part is carried out. First, the roughing allowance is removed in several passes, then it is adjusted to the required size. Stopping the rotation of the spindle, a template is applied to the stationary workpiece several times, the maximum and minimum diameters of the handle are measured in order to bring its shape to the specified dimensions in a few passes. In order to speed up the cutting process, the longitudinal movement is set to automatic mode, leaving manual control for the transverse caliper.

The sequence of processing the shaped surface of the handle with a cool cutter using longitudinal and transverse feeds: a – the finished part; b, c and d – semi-finished products to obtain the part; A, B, C, D, E and G - the surfaces to be processed.

When working with a copier, a special device is used, complete with a copier 5, a rod 3 with a finger 4. The finger 4, slipping along the copier, ensures the movement of the rod connected to the caliper, moving it and the cutting tool mounted on it in accordance with the contour of the copier. The stroke of the caliper in the longitudinal direction is recommended to be performed in automatic mode, the transverse feed is turned off. The tool, repeating the thrust movement, forms the relief of the rotating workpiece.

Processing of shaped surfaces by copier: 1 – cutter, 2- handle, 3 – rod, 4 – finger, 5 - copier

Use of shaped cutters

It is advisable to produce small-length parts using cutters with a working edge that exactly matches the specified contour. A prerequisite for the exact fulfillment of the technical parameters of cutting – the front surface of the cutting tool must be located at the level of the line of the centers of the lathe. The front surface is used to sharpen the cutters for shaped processing, which is important to take into account if there is a need for their repeated installation. It should be checked that the cutter is installed perpendicular to the machine center line – this condition significantly affects the quality and purity of the cut. The perpendicularity is checked using a square, one edge of which is located in the direction of the axis of the part, the other along one of the sides of the cutter. The body of the cutter in cross section can be

round and rectangular – this facilitates the processing of surfaces with complex relief.

The place of installation of prismatic radial shaped cutters is a horizontal revolver head or a transverse caliper. The line of the cutting edge of the shaped cutter must be at the level of the center fixed in the spindle or in the centers of the part. The dimensions of the rear corners α can be set by adjusting the position of the cutter in the holder, which is quite convenient at the stage of preparatory work.

In metalworking industries, preference is usually given to cutters with screw forming cutting edges compared to cutters in which the cutting edges are made in the form of ring forming. This is due to the fact that the surface treated with screw forming cutters is less rough, at the same time the cutting process is much faster.

The high productivity of the cutters with a screw forming the cutting edge is fully used when they are installed in the turret. To improve the cutting quality, a uniform feed of no more than 0.05 mm / rev is used with a cutter width of 10... 20 mm. Wider shaped cutters (with a width of more than 20 mm) are designed to feed up to 0.03 mm/rev.

Methods of control of shaped surfaces

The main way to control the shaped surfaces of parts is a template, with which the profile of the part obtained as a result of processing is checked. If the dimensions of the part have deviations from the drawing, the reasons could be factors such as processing errors, inaccuracies in the cutting parameters of the cutter, errors in its installation. It is also possible that the deviations occurred due to deformations of the product during processing - in this case, the supply of the cutting tool should be reduced.

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